

EFFECT OF OF ALKALOID IN ASHWAGANDHA ROOT EXTRACT ON THYROID INDICES AMONG HYPOTHYROID WOMEN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16976482>

Keywords

Ashwagandha root extract, Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH), Triiodothyronine (T3), Thyroxine (T4), Body fat percentage (BF %), Hypothyroidism.

Article History

Received: 26 May, 2025

Accepted: 05 August, 2025

Published: 27 August, 2025

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Abstract

Hypothyroidism is characterized by a condition in which the body doesn't produce sufficient thyroid hormones which affects 3%–8% of people globally (Taylor et al., 2018). In Pakistan 6-10% of females are affected by hypothyroidism respectively (Alam Khan et al., 2002)) Ashwagandha root extract contains active ingredient withaferin-A (alkaloid) that effects both the axis of hypothalamus–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) and hypothalamus–pituitary–thyroid (HPT) thus normalizing the thyroid hormone level activity by negative feedback inhibition (Dongre et al., 2015). This study has aimed to evaluate the effect of alkaloid in ashwagandha root extract on TSH, T3 and T4 among hypothyroid women.

Methodology: The study was conducted among 64 participants with BMI 25.0 – 29.9 and who meet the inclusion exclusion criteria. First, all the participants were divided in to two groups; control group (n=32) and intervention group (n=32). The participants were selected from London Aesthetics and Rejuvenation center Gynae OPD and Medicine OPD, Lahore. All the participants were advised to take conventional medicines (as per physician recommendation). While the intervention group participants were advised take 600mg/day of Ashwagandha root extract containing alkaloid as active ingredient daily for 10 weeks. It was requested that the participants do not change their usual exercise routine and refrain from using any additional dietary supplements. The lab test for thyroid hormones, TSH, T3 and T4 were collected on 0 week and after 10th week of study. Body fat percentage was also measured at 0 week and then after 10th week.

Results: Average mean age of conventional treatment group was 24.53 ± 3.47 and intervention group was 22.84 ± 5.07. The mean difference of BMI pre and post treatment in conventional treatment group is 25.14±3.505 to 24.28±2.89 and intervention group is 25.37± 2.22 to 24.27±2.55. The mean difference of T3 in pre-treatment was 1.14± 0.16 to post treatment 1.27± 0.303 and T4 pre-

treatment 52.7 ± 27.33 to post treatment 57.57 ± 29.7 . The reduction of TSH and body fat were also observed. The mean difference of TSH level pre and post treatment (6.76 ± 0.555 to 5.04 ± 0.734) in intervention group.

Conclusion: Ashwagandha root extract showed significant mean difference in reduction of BMI, Body fat and TSH level in participants ($p = 0.001$). There is significant mean difference in T3 and T4 level were also observed.

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Historical perspective

Hypothyroidism is the condition when triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4) are not produced sufficiently by thyroid gland in your body to maintain overall metabolism. Due to the loss of negative feedback inhibition, thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) in blood from anterior pituitary gland is increased leading to hypothyroidism. (Rehman, Zafar, Fatima, Mohib, & Sheikh, 2020).

As it controls almost every physiological process occurring in body, dysfunction of thyroid gland can lead to various metabolic abnormalities including weight gain, infertility, dyslipidemia, menstrual abnormalities, neuromuscular dysfunction and cognitive impairment (Gaitonde, Rowley, & Sweeney, 2012). Thyroid hormone directly effects metabolism of fats, protein and carbohydrates by regulating the expense of basal metabolic rate. Indirectly, it also effects how insulin and catecholamines work, as these help to regulate normal body weight (Abdel-Wahhab *et al.*, 2019).

This common endocrine disorder called hypothyroidism effects almost 3-8 % of total population globally. The prevalence of hypothyroidism in females of reproductive age is estimated to be 6-10% as compared to males that is 2.4-3% globally (Taylor *et al.*, 2018). Most of the recent European studies estimated 0.75% of incidence rate of hypothyroidism in men and women that is 51 cases per 100,000 of people every year. Recent report of National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III) depicts that almost 13 million of Americans in United States have undiagnosed hypothyroidism and every one in total of 300 persons in United States has reported hypothyroidism (Gaitonde *et al.*, 2012). However, in Pakistan, the prevalence of

hypothyroidism is almost 5.1 % (Alam Khan, Khan, & Akhtar, 2002).

Hypothyroidism is classified further into three types primary, secondary and tertiary hypothyroidism. Primary hypothyroidism depicts that there is insufficiency of thyroid hormones produced by thyroid gland although it is stimulated properly. Almost 95% of hypothyroid people are suffering from Primary hypothyroidism. It is further classified into different stages that is overt hypothyroidism which is characterized by increase production of (TSH) and low production of (T4). Second stage is sub-clinical hypothyroidism characterized by raised level of (TSH) but T4 is at normal level. In this stage there is no symptoms of thyroid dysfunction. Secondary and tertiary hypothyroidism is characterized by a condition when your thyroid hormone is not stimulating properly to produce sufficient thyroid hormones. This is due to the dysfunction of pituitary gland or hypothalamus (Almandoz & Gharib, 2012).

Hypothyroidism symptoms varies in every woman depending upon the age and other factors. Most of the common sign and symptoms includes weight gain, slow metabolism, menstrual cycle abnormalities, muscles stiffness, inability to tolerate cold temperature, delayed motor neuron activity, sleep apnea, hair loss, dry skin, cognitive decline and constipation. These sign and symptoms are not considered the exact parameter to diagnose hypothyroidism. It can be diagnosed with the help of laboratory findings of TSH, T3 and T4 levels in blood. Raised levels of TSH is the first and main indication of hypothyroidism. (Gupta & Rana, 2007). Other laboratory results in hypothyroidism have also been linked to anemia, hypoxia and hyponatremia. The causes of development of hypothyroidism have also been linked to the iodine deficiency, dysfunction of

pituitary gland, hypothalamus, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, or it can also be due to the birth defect which is very rare (SPENCER, 1988).

Treatment of hypothyroidism should be specified for female patients on the basis of their concerns and needs. It should target the metabolic abnormalities with the help of dietary interventions, healthy lifestyle and physical activity. Ashwagandha (*Withania Somnifera*) is an Indian herb by origin which is also commonly called Asganda. It has represented a promising nutritional treatment in various hormonal disorders including thyroid abnormalities and goiter (Gill et al., 2019). It stabilizes the physiological processes, maintaining the homeostasis and revitalizing every tissue of body. It is well known of its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and hypotensive properties (Singh, Bhalla, de Jager, & Gilca, 2011).

According to the proximate analysis of ashwagandha extract powder per (100g) constitutes of ash 4.41 g. Nutrient composition depicts protein 3.9g, fiber comes out to be 32.3 g, fat 0.3g, and carbohydrate 49.9g. Micronutrients includes iron 3.3g, calcium 23mg and vitamin C 5.8g (Kumari & Gupta, 2016). Ashwagandha root extract contains variety of alkaloids including tannins, lactones, glucosides, steryl glucosides and withanolides. Withferin A and withanolide A that is considered pharmacologically active ingredient to improve insulin activity and helps to increase the uptake of glucose thus maintaining blood sugar level in patients with type 2 diabetes (Kaul, 1957).

The Alkaloids in Ashwagandha extract is beneficial for thyroid hormone activity as it acts on the axis of hypothalamus–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) which responses inversely on the axis of (HPT) hypothalamus–pituitary–thyroid (Elgar et al., 2011). As increased production of cortisol can inhibit the axis of HPT which in turn helps to normalize the level of thyroid hormones TSH, T3 and T4 by a mechanism of negative feedback inhibition (Sunanda Panda & Kar, 1998). Ashwagandha root extract exhibits anti-inflammatory effect on both HPT and HPA axis (Dongre, Langade, & Bhattacharyya, 2015). It can also affect the thyroid hormone activity directly according to most of the animal studies (Chung, 2014). The presence of phytonutrients in the

Ashwagandha root extract refers it as adaptogen which helps to maintain metabolism, reduces stress, improves physical fitness and brain health (Abascal & Yarnell, 2003). Supplementation of Ashwagandha root extract is considered as effective ergogenic aid while doing exercising by reducing the stress response (Wankhede, Langade, Joshi, Sinha, & Bhattacharyya, 2015).

Epidemiological studies show that ashwagandha root extract can also be used in management of body weight in chronically stressed women. It is referred as anti-stress agent that helps in recovery as well as improves overall performance of body functions (Cannataro, Straface, & Cione, 2022).

Material and Method

This cross-sectional study conducted among 64 participants who meet the inclusion criteria. First, all the participants were divided in to two groups; conventional treatment group (n=32) and intervention group (n=32). All the individuals were taking conventional treatment. However, the intervention group participants were taking 600mg/day of ashwagandha root extract for 10 weeks (Sharma et al., 2018). The participants were requested not to alter their routine physical activity and not to take any other nutritional supplement. The lab test for TSH, T3, T4 and body fat percentage, were collected on 0, 4th, 8th and after 10th week. The follow up questionnaire of anthropometric measurements were filled by both group on 0, 4th, 8th and after 10th week.

Procurement of material:

Ashwagandha root extract capsules (300mg) procure from London Aesthetics and Rejuvenation Centre, Lahore. The follow up was conducted with the help of questionnaire on 1st week of study, 4th, 8th and 10th week of study. The anthropometric measurements and body fat percentage were collected at 1st visit and then after 10th week of all enrolled participants. Following parameters were checked and compared such as BMI, body fat percentage and weight. After 10th weeks of study, the same protocol of baseline visit was conducted. The pre- and post- test study data was compared to test the hypothesis. Lab tests such as TSH, T3 and T4 were compared. Concerns related to body fat percentage and weight were also compared. For

Total TSH, T3 and T4 2cc blood sample of each participant was taken with the help of syringe. Serum-based immunoassays and LC-MS/MS techniques were used for measuring TSH, T3 and T4 in blood. Body Fat Percentage using Omron body composition monitor. Age and height of each participant were added in body composition monitor. Each patient was asked to remove shoes and place their feet on electrodes while grasping other two electrodes by fingers. Their arms while holding electrodes were in straight position. After one minute of holding the electrodes, each patient was asked to release the electrodes free. Body composition monitor showed body fat percentage automatically on screen of machine.

Sample Size:

The sample size was calculated with the help of following parameters such as TSH, T3 and T4 keeping the power of study equal to 84 percent and level of significance equal to 5 percent with 20 percent expected dropout the sample of subjects would be enrolled in the study. The total sample size was 64 of total female participants.

Sample Selection:

Inclusion Criteria: Participants of age 18-30 years. Patients having serum high total TSH level between 4.5-10 mIU/L was be enrolled in study (Sharma *et al.*, 2018). Patients between the age of 18-30 years was enrolled in current study (Sharma *et al.*, 2018). Patients having body mass index less between 25-29.9kg/m² was enrolled in study.

Exclusion Criteria: Pregnant and lactating

mothers. Patients who are already taking other nutritional supplements, hypotensive, beta-blockers, inhaled beta agonists, hormonal contraceptives, corticosteroids within prior 3 months was excluded from experimental group. (Sharma *et al.*, 2018). Patients having body mass index less than 30 kg/m² (Sharma *et al.*, 2018). Patients with any other systemic, immunologic, or inflammatory diseases was not included in the trial. Patients who are participating in any other research study.

Statistical analysis Data was entered and subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS version 25. Mean \pm standard deviation was used for quantitative variables for example weight, BMI, Lab tests. Frequency and percentage were used for qualitative variables for example Age and follow up questionnaire. Paired sample t-test was used for the comparison of lab tests, weight, BMI of both groups (conventional treatment group and intervention group) before and after treatments. The level of significance was taken as ($p \leq 0.05$).

Results

Total 64 female patients with hypothyroidism between the age of 18-30 were enrolled in this study. They were divided into two groups. Group 1 was conventional group which was on normal diet and treatment and group two was intervention group which was on ashwagandha root extract 600mg/ day. Pre and post treatment test were conducted for both groups.

Table 4.1. Mean \pm SD and Percentage change of T3 of both groups Pre and Post treatment.

S.No	Parameter	Conventional treatmentgroup		Intervention group	
		Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD	Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD
1.	T3	1.13 \pm 0.106	1.14 \pm 0.099	1.14 \pm 0.16	1.27 \pm 0.303
2.	P value	0.11		0.002	
3.	% Change	0.88		11.40	

Table 4.1. represents the significance difference of mean \pm S.D and percentage change of T3 of conventional treatment group and intervention group participants. The mean \pm S.D of conventional treatment group in pre-treatment was

1.13 \pm 0.106 and it Increases to 1.14 \pm 0.099 in post treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of T3 of

conventional treatment group participants was 0.88 percent. The significance level $p=0.11$. The mean \pm SD of intervention group in pre-treatment was 1.14 ± 0.16 and it increases to 1.27 ± 0.303 in post treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan and ashwagandha root on save dosage 300 mg/day for

10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of weight of intervention group participants was 11.40 percent. The significance level $p=0.002$. The results show that the average mean T3 was Increase more in intervention group participants as compared to the conventional treatment group participants.

Table 4.2. Mean \pm SD and Percentage change of T4 of both groups' participants in Pre and Post treatment.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Conventional treatmentgroup		Intervention group	
		Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD	Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD
1.	T4	53.69 \pm 27.07	54.39 \pm 27.07	52.7 \pm 27.33	57.57 \pm 29.7
2.	P value	0.000		0.0005	
3.	% Change	1.30		9.24	

Table 4.2. represents the significance difference of mean \pm S.D and percentage change of T4 of conventional treatment group and intervention group participants. The mean \pm S.D of conventional treatment group in pre-treatment was 53.69 ± 27.07 and it increases to 54.39 ± 27.07 in post treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of weight of conventional treatment group participants was 1.30 percent. The significance level $p=0.000$. The mean \pm SD of intervention group in pre-treatment was 52.7 ± 27.33 and it increases to

57.28 ± 6.50 in post treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan and Ashwagandha root on save dosage 300 mg/day for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of weight of intervention group participants was 9.24 percent. The significance level $p=0.0005$. The results shows that the average mean T4 was increases more in intervention group participants as compared to the conventional treatment group participants.

Table 4.3. Mean \pm SD and Percentage change of TSH of both groups participants in Pre and Post treatment.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Conventional treatmentgroup		Intervention group	
		Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD	Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD
1.	TSH	6.76 \pm 0.822	6.65 \pm 0.808	6.76 \pm 0.555	5.04 \pm 0.734
2.	P value	0.01		0.000	
3.	% Change	-1.62		-25.4	

Table 4.3. represents the significance difference of mean \pm S.D and percentage change of TSH of conventional treatment group and intervention group participants. The mean \pm S.D of conventional treatment group in pre-treatment was 69.96 ± 7.46 and it reduced to 6.65 ± 0.808 in post treatment. This group participants were taking

conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of TSH of conventional treatment group participants was -1.62 percent which was shown with -ive sign which represents the reduction in TSH in post treatment as compared to pre-treatment. The significance level $p=0.01$.

The mean \pm SD of intervention group in pre-treatment was 6.76 ± 0.555 and it reduced to 5.04 ± 0.734 in post treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan and Ashwagandha root on save dosage 300 mg/day for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of TSH of intervention group participants

was -25.4 percent which was shown with -ive sign which represents the reduction in TSH in post treatment as compared to pre-treatment. The significance level $p=0.000$. The results show that the average mean TSH was reduced more in intervention group participants as compared to the conventional treatment group participants.

Table 4.4. Mean \pm SD and Percentage change of Body Fat of both groups participants in Pre and Post treatment.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Conventional treatmentgroup		Intervention group	
		Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD	Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD
1.	Body Fat	26.78 \pm 2.08	26.29 \pm 2.1	26.60 \pm 1.733	25.22 \pm 2.247
2.	P value	0.02		0.000	
3.	% Change	-1.82		-5.47	

Table 4.4. represents the significance difference of mean \pm S.D and percentage change of body fat of conventional treatment group and intervention group participants. The mean \pm SD of conventional treatment group in pre-treatment was 26.78 ± 2.08 and it reduced to 26.29 ± 2.1 in post treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of weight of conventional treatment group participants was -1.82 percent which was shown with -ive sign which represents the reduction in body fat in post treatment as compared to pre-treatment. The significance level $p=0.02$.

25.22 ± 2.247 in post treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan and ashwagandha root on save dosage 300 mg/day for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of body fat of intervention group participants was -5.47 percent which was shown with -ive sign which represents the reduction in body fat in post treatment as compared to pre-treatment. The significance level $p=0.000$. The results shows that the average mean body fat was reduced more in intervention group participants as compared to the conventional treatment group participants.

The mean \pm SD of intervention group in pre-treatment was 26.60 ± 1.733 and it reduced to

Table 4.5. Mean \pm SD and Percentage change of BMI of both groups' participants in Pre and Post treatment.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Conventional treatmentgroup		Intervention group	
		Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD	Pre-treatment mean \pm SD	Post treatment mean \pm SD
1.	BMI	25.14 \pm 3.505	24.28 \pm 2.89	25.37 \pm 2.22	24.27 \pm 2.55
2.	P value	0.000		0.01	
3.	% Change	-3.54		-4.53	

Table 4.1.2. represents the significance difference of mean \pm S.D and percentage change of body mass index of conventional treatment group and

intervention group participants. The mean \pm SD of conventional treatment group in pre-treatment was 25.14 ± 3.505 and it reduced to 24.28 ± 2.89 in post

treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of BMI of conventional treatment group participants was -3.54 percent which was shown with -ive sign which represents the reduction in BMI in post treatment as compared to pre-treatment. The significance level $p=0.000$.

The mean \pm SD of intervention group in pre-treatment was 25.37 ± 2.22 and it reduced to 24.27 ± 2.55 in post treatment. This group participants were taking conventional treatment medicines along with modified diet plan and ashwagandha root on save dosage 300 mg/day for 10 weeks of study therefore, the average percentage change of BMI of intervention group participants was -4.53 percent which was shown with -ive sign which represents the reduction in BMI in post treatment as compared to pre-treatment. The significance level $p=0.01$. The results show that the average mean BMI was reduced more in intervention group participants as compared to the conventional treatment group participants.

Discussion:

Hypothyroidism is the condition when your thyroid gland does not produce sufficient thyroid hormones that is triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine(T4) in your body to maintain overall metabolism. Hypothyroidism leads to increased production of thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) from anterior pituitary gland due to loss of negative feedback inhibition (Rehman *et al.*, 2020). Almost 95% of hypothyroid people are suffering from Primary hypothyroidism. It is further classified into different stages that is overt hypothyroidism which is characterized by increase production of (TSH) and low production of (T4). Sharma *et al.*, conducted a double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. He took 50 patients with mild hypothyroidism (TSH 4.5–10 IU/l). Patients were divided into two groups of control and placebo. They were asked to take ashwagandha root extract 300mg/ twice a day for 8 weeks. TSH, T3 and T4 were assessed. Results have shown the improvement in level of thyroid hormones. Final improvements come out to be 17.4 %, 19.6% and 41.5% on subsequent weeks respectively. Results

were significant as compared to placebo group. For TSH ($p < 0.001$), T3 ($p = 0.0031$), and T4 ($p = 0.0096$) in treatment group. This study has showed the positive effect of ashwagandha root extract on thyroid indices in hypothyroid women (Sharma *et al.*, 2018). According to our study 64 female patients were enrolled for 10 weeks and they were divided into two groups one group was conventional group and other was intervention group. Conventional group was on normal diet and treatment, while intervention group was on ashwagandha root extract added with diet 600 mg/day. Pre and post-tests were conducted. Results was analyzed. TSH, T3 and T4 showed statistically significant result $p = 0.05$. which shows that ashwagandha root extract is effective for hypothyroidism patients.

A study was conducted to evaluate Laboratory indices of thyroid function (TSH, Free T4, and T3) in a randomized clinical trial in which they were checked the effect of ashwagandha in patients with bipolar disorder to improve cognitive functions. They took total of 60 patients. Since this research was not carried out to specifically examine thyroid function in relation with ashwagandha in bipolar patients. One ASW- treated patient had subclinical hypothyroidism (TSH - 5.7 mIU/L) at baseline that normalized to (6.96 mIU/L), Results has showed that T4 increases from baseline value (7%, 12%, and 24%) in ASW treated group. In placebo group 6 of total 7 patients showed decreased level of T4 from baseline values (4% to 23%). This 8- week of study has showed the that ashwagandha may increase T4 levels(Gannon *et al.*, 2014). In our study the intervention group was on ashwagandha root extract, post treatment test showed T3 and T4 level was increased after using ashwagandha root extract and TSH level was decreased. And the values of TSH, T3 and T4 was statistically significant $p= 0.05$.

In a study author determined the efficiency of ashwagandha root extract in sub clinical hypothyroid patients. A detailed analysis revealed that daily treatment with ashwagandha for a period of 8 weeks produced a significant decrease in serum TSH level ($p < 0.01$) and an increase in serum T3 ($p < 0.01$) and T4 (0.01) levels(Sharma *et al.*, 2018). In this study was done for period of 10 weeks, the detailed analysis revealed that daily

treatment with ashwagandha root extract, produced significant decrease in serum TSH level ($p < 0.05$) and significant increase in T3 and T4 levels ($p < 0.05$).

In a study the author describes about his study that ashwagandha treatment was effective to normalized the thyroid indices during the 8 weeks treatment period in a significant manner. Treatment with ashwagandha root extracts was found safe and tolerable, with few mild and temporary adverse events. (Sharma et al., 2018) The results of the this study are accordance to previous studies (S Panda & Kar, 1999).

The importance of ashwagandha root extract in the regulation of thyroid function was explained in a study. P value for T4 and T3 concentrations showed significant results as compared to the control group ($P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.05$) for T3 and T4. Mean standard deviation for T4 control was 52.2 ± 11.5 and for treatment group 110 ± 6.2 . Mean standard deviation for T3 control was 2.2 ± 0.1 and for treatment group 12.6 ± 0.1 (Sunanda Panda & Kar, 1998). In this study ashwagandha root extract also shows positive results. Mean \pm SD value of T3 and T4 for the intervention group was 1.27 ± 0.303 and 57.57 ± 29.7 and TSH value was 5.04 ± 0.734 . and p-value was statistically significant.

The results indicate a possible role for ashwagandha in regulating hypothalamic-pituitary- thyroid axis (Chandrasekhar, Kapoor, & Anishetty, 2012). In another study body fat percentage was calculated with a bioelectrical impedance method using machine with electrodes placed at the hand, wrist, foot, and ankle (Numon, Warphea, & Birnbaum, 2019; Sharma et al., 2018). In our study body fat was decreased after taking 600mg/ day of root extract of ashwagandha. The percentage change of intervention group was -5.47. and p value was 0.000. That means ashwagandha root extract shows effect on hypothyroidism patients.

Conclusion

Hypothyroidism is a condition that occurs not only in female but also in male. But in this study, only females were enrolled of age between 18-30 years. They were divided into two groups. One was on normal diet and treatment and other was on ashwagandha root extract. The pre and post

treatment test were conducted. According to results Ashwagandha roots have alkaloids which is very helpful in hypothyroidism. We concluded in this study that level of TSH is reduces after using ashwagandha root extract in diet. And the level of T3 and T4 was increased. That means ashwagandha root is helpful in reduction of weight, BMI, body fat and TSH level and increase in T3 and T4 levels.

REFERENCES

- Abascal, K., & Yarnell, E. (2003). Increasing vitality with adaptogens: multifaceted herbs for treating physical and mental stress. *Alternative & Complementary Therapies*, 9(2), 54-60.
- Abdel-Wahhab, K. G., Mourad, H. H., Mannaa, F. A., Morsy, F. A., Hassan, L. K., & Taher, R. F. (2019). Role of ashwagandha methanolic extract in the regulation of thyroid profile in hypothyroidism modeled rats. *Molecular biology reports*, 46(4), 3637-3649.
- Alam Khan, V., Khan, M. A., & Akhtar, S. (2002). Thyroid disorders, etiology and prevalence. *J Med Sci*, 2(2), 89-94.
- Almandoz, J. P., & Gharib, H. (2012). Hypothyroidism: etiology, diagnosis, and management. *Medical Clinics*, 96(2), 203-221.
- Biswal, B. M., Sulaiman, S. A., Ismail, H. C., Zakaria, H., & Musa, K. I. (2013). Effect of *Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha) on the development of chemotherapy-induced fatigue and quality of life in breast cancer patients. *Integrative cancer therapies*, 12(4), 312-322.
- Cannataro, R., Straface, N., & Cione, E. (2022). Nutritional supplements in combat sports: What we know and what we do. *Human Nutrition & Metabolism*, 200155.
- Chandrasekhar, K., Kapoor, J., & Anishetty, S. (2012). A prospective, randomized double-blind, placebo-controlled study of safety and efficacy of a high-concentration full-spectrum extract of ashwagandha root in reducing stress and anxiety in adults. *Indian journal of psychological medicine*, 34(3), 255-262.

- Chung, H. R. (2014). Iodine and thyroid function. *Annals of pediatric endocrinology & metabolism*, 19(1), 8.
- Cohen, S. M., Mukerji, R., Timmermann, B. N., Samadi, A. K., & Cohen, M. S. (2012). A novel combination of withaferin A and sorafenib shows synergistic efficacy against both papillary and anaplastic thyroid cancers. *The American journal of surgery*, 204(6), 895-901.
- Deurenberg, P., Pieters, J. J., & Hautvast, J. G. (1990). The assessment of the body fat percentage by skinfold thickness measurements in childhood and young adolescence. *British Journal of nutrition*, 63(2), 293-303.
- Dongre, S., Langade, D., & Bhattacharyya, S. (2015). Efficacy and safety of Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) root extract in improving sexual function in women: a pilot study. *BioMed Research International*, 2015.
- Fattah, C., Farah, N., O'Toole, F., Barry, S., Stuart, B., & Turner, M. J. (2009). Body Mass Index (BMI) in women booking for antenatal care: comparison between self-reported and digital measurements. *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, 144(1), 32-34.
- Gaitonde, D. Y., Rowley, K. D., & Sweeney, L. B. (2012). Hypothyroidism: an update. *South African Family Practice*, 54(5), 384-390.
- Gannon, J. M., Brar, J., Rai, A., & Chengappa, K. R. (2019). Effects of a standardized extract of *Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha) on depression and anxiety symptoms in persons with schizophrenia participating in a randomized, placebo-controlled clinical trial. *Ann Clin Psychiatry*, 31(2), 123-129.
- Gannon, J. M., Forrest, P. E., & Chengappa, K. R. (2014). Subtle changes in thyroid indices during a placebo-controlled study of an extract of *Withania somnifera* in persons with bipolar disorder. *Journal of Ayurveda and integrative medicine*, 5(4), 241.
- Gill, M. K., Kumar, S., Sharma, M., Singh, T. P., Kumar, K., & Kaur, R. (2019). Role of Ashwagandha Incorporated Functional Foods for Betterment of Human Health: A Review. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering and Food Technology* p-ISSN, 2350-0085.
- Gupta, G. L., & Rana, A. (2007). *Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha): a review. *Pharmacognosy Reviews*, 1(1).
- Jatwa, R., & Kar, A. (2009). Amelioration of metformin-induced hypothyroidism by *Withania somnifera* and *Bauhinia purpurea* extracts in type 2 diabetic mice. *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives*, 23(8), 1140-1145.
- Kamal, H. I., Patel, K., Brdak, A., Heffernan, J., & Ahmad, N. (2022). Ashwagandha as a Unique Cause of Thyrotoxicosis Presenting With Supraventricular Tachycardia. *Cureus*, 14(3).
- Kaul, K. (1957). The origin, distribution and cultivation of Ashwagandha the so called *Withania somnifera* of Indian literature. Paper presented at the Symposium on the Utilization of Indian Medicinal Plants. Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi.
- Kumari, S., & Gupta, A. (2016). Nutritional composition of dehydrated ashwagandha, shatavari, and ginger root powder. *International Journal of Home Science*, 2(3), 68-70.
- Kushwaha, S., Betsy, A., & Chawla, P. (2012). Effect of Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) root powder supplementation in treatment of hypertension. *Studies on Ethno-Medicine*, 6(2), 111-115.
- Leyon, P., & Kuttan, G. (2004). Effect of *Withania somnifera* on B16F-10 melanoma induced metastasis in mice. *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives*, 18(2), 118-122.

- Lopresti, A. L., Drummond, P. D., & Smith, S. J. (2019). A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, crossover study examining the hormonal and vitality effects of ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) in aging, overweight males. *American Journal of Men's Health*, 13(2), 1557988319835985.
- Masood, S., Yousafzai, A., Asif, M., Ahamd, K. N., Ali, I., Sultan, N., . . . Mustafa, M. Z. Prevalence of hypothyroid disease: A cross sectional study at a higher rate among young male and female population of Balochistan, Pakistan.
- Mohanty, I., Arya, D. S., Dinda, A., Talwar, K. K., Joshi, S., & Gupta, S. K. (2004). Mechanisms of cardioprotective effect of *Withania somnifera* in experimentally induced myocardial infarction. *Basic & clinical pharmacology & toxicology*, 94(4), 184-190.
- Numon, M., Warphea, J., & Birnbaum, L. (2019). A Physiological Profile of Intermediate Crossfit Athletes: A Pilot Study. *Journal of Sport and Human Performance*, 7(2).
- Panda, S., & Kar, A. (1998). Changes in thyroid hormone concentrations after administration of ashwagandha root extract to adult male mice. *Journal of pharmacy and pharmacology*, 50(9), 1065-1068.
- Panda, S., & Kar, A. (1999). *Withania somnifera* and *Bauhinia purpurea* in the regulation of circulating thyroid hormone concentrations in female mice. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 67(2), 233-239.
- Raut, A. A., Rege, N. N., Tadv, F. M., Solanki, P. V., Kene, K. R., Shirolkar, S. G., . . . Vaidya, A. B. (2012). Exploratory study to evaluate tolerability, safety, and activity of Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) in healthy volunteers. *Journal of Ayurveda and integrative medicine*, 3(3), 111.
- Rehman, R., Zafar, A., Fatima, S. S., Mohib, A., & Sheikh, A. (2020). Altered sperm parameters and subclinical hypothyroidism; A cross sectional study in Karachi, Pakistan. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*, 74(9), e13555.
- Saiyed, A., Jahan, N., Makbul, S. A. A., Ansari, M., Bano, H., & Habib, S. H. (2016). Effect of combination of *Withania somnifera* Dunal and *Tribulus terrestris* Linn on letrozole induced polycystic ovarian syndrome in rats. *Integrative medicine research*, 5(4), 293-300.
- Sharma, A. K., Basu, I., & Singh, S. (2018). Efficacy and safety of ashwagandha root extract in subclinical hypothyroid patients: a double-blind, randomized placebo-controlled trial. *The Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*, 24(3), 243-248.
- Singh, N., Bhalla, M., de Jager, P., & Gilca, M. (2011). An overview on ashwagandha: a Rasayana (rejuvenator) of Ayurveda. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 8(5S).
- SPENCER, C. A. (1988). Clinical utility and cost-effectiveness of sensitive thyrotropin assays in ambulatory and hospitalized patients. Paper presented at the Mayo Clinic Proceedings.
- Taylor, P. N., Albrecht, D., Scholz, A., Gutierrez-Buey, G., Lazarus, J. H., Dayan, C. M., & Okosieme, O. E. (2018). Global epidemiology of hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*, 14(5), 301-316.
- Tiwari, S., Gupta, S. K., & Pathak, A. K. (2021). A double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial on the effect of Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera* dunal.) root extract in improving cardiorespiratory endurance and recovery in healthy athletic adults. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 272, 113929.
- Verma, N., Gupta, S. K., Tiwari, S., & Mishra, A. K. (2021). Safety of ashwagandha root extract: a randomized, placebo-controlled, study in healthy volunteers. *Complementary therapies in medicine*, 57, 102642.

Visavadiya, N. P., & Narasimhacharya, A. (2007). Hypocholesteremic and antioxidant effects of *Withania somnifera* (Dunal) in hypercholesteremic rats. *Phytomedicine*, 14(2-3), 136-142.

Wankhede, S., Langade, D., Joshi, K., Sinha, S. R., & Bhattacharyya, S. (2015). Examining the effect of *Withania somnifera* supplementation on muscle strength and recovery: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of the International Society of Sports Nutrition*, 12(1), 1-11.

